

University-School Partnerships: Successes and Challenges in Designing and Implementing
Strategies to Promote Racial Equity

Although the landmark legislation, *Brown v. Board of Education* brought about integration in schools in 1954, significant and unyielding racial inequities persist in American education (Ladson-Billings, 2006; Love, 2004). Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC) have a fundamentally unequal learning experience, as they attend schools with fewer resources, are more likely to be exposed to exclusionary discipline, and are less likely to be tracked into advanced classes (Carter et al., 2017; Ladson-Billings, 2006). Notwithstanding meaningful efforts to create more equitable schools, significant racial inequities remain (Merolla & Jackson, 2019). Partnerships such as university-assisted community schools (UACS) have been recognized as a promising model that can support schools with addressing persistent racial disparities (Harkavy et al., 2013; Harkavy & Hartley, 2009; Authors, 2019). Racial equity efforts often fall short by neglecting to address power differentials, resistance to change, or buy-in from school staff (Lynch et al., 2017; Authors 2000). In reflecting on our process of building a UACS partnership to center youth voices to advance racial equity, we discuss important successes and challenges that emerged at two schools in one district. We explore the following research question: How do UACS partnerships support the design and implementation of school-based racial equity strategies?

Racial Equity in Schools

Racial equity in schools is both a process and an outcome. It is a process aimed at eliminating root causes that lead to race differences in student experiences and outcomes, as well as the deliberate development, implementation, and continuous improvement of school-based policies and practices that improve the opportunities, experiences and outcomes of BIPOC students (Espinoza, 2007; *Racial Equity Toolkit Glossary*, n.d.). Such processes include interrupting racial bias, prejudice, and stigmatization of BIPOC students, implementing culturally-sustaining curriculum and pedagogies, and addressing the institutional racism in

school structures (Chavous et al., 2008; Dixson et al., 2006; Howard, 2010; Ladson-Billings, 2014; Paris & Alim, 2017). The work of racial equity in schools is twofold; It must facilitate individual and collective critical race consciousness among individuals in the school community while also enacting anti-racist changes in schools (Welton et al., 2018). These changes include official and informal policy and practice across the classroom, school, and district levels.

The aims of racial justice need to be reflected in the process of pursuing racial equity in schools. This includes the research and collection of data used to inform school planning and action taking. A variety of participatory approaches have been used to research, design and implement racial equity initiatives in schools. However, a shared feature is to center the experiential knowledge of those most affected by the issue, and to prioritize the use of information for action (Cargo & Mercer, 2008; Vaughn & Jacquez, 2020). In this context, sharing power and decision-making in the school improvement planning process with students and educators of color is fundamental. Thus, we adopted a university-school partnership model to center the voices of BIPOC as the experts of their lived experiences that have different histories and experiences with racism that must be considered (Delgado & Stefancic, 2017).

University-School Partnerships to Promote Racial Equity

UACS provide a practical approach for democratic transformation (Harkavy et al., 2013). "Community schools" are based on the idea that similar to universities, public schools can serve as community "focal points," galvanizing community services, institutions, and organizations (Harkavy et al., 2013). This framework positions universities as hubs for developing innovative approaches to education (Harkavy et al., 2013; Luter et al., 2013). As such, this model is well suited to promote racial equity in schools. Comprehensive models of UACS take many years and significant investment to create and sustain. We present here a partnership in the early stages that focused on building the partnership, demonstrating the benefits, and assessing feasibility.

Our work was a research-practice partnership (Coburn et al., 2013) focused on racial equity and youth voice (Authors, 2019). The research alliance formed between the university research team and school district, maintained the hallmarks of research-practice partnerships by focusing on a problem of practice, a commitment to mutualism, a focus on building the partnership, and the production of original analyses (Coburn et al., 2013). Developing a project based on a problem of practice determined by school partners is parallel to the “process” characterized in the UACS model, whereby schools are situated as the experts on their own communities. (Coburn et al., 2013; Harkavy & Hartley, 2009). Likewise, mutualism is similar to the UACS goal of creating a product that “makes a positive difference for all partners” (p.12, (Harkavy & Hartley, 2009). Like other UACS projects, our place-based model is a participatory approach to school improvement that uses data to inform practice improvement strategies (Lawson et al., 2016). In this paper, we explore successes and challenges in four phases of the research-practice partnership: (1) building the partnership, (2) designing the project, (3) data analysis, and (4) translating the data into action for racial justice.

Methods

This paper outlines the results of a multisite case study with students, teachers and administrators across two racially and ethnically diverse middle schools in one school district in the Pacific Northwest. We used a multisite case study approach (N=2) (Yin, 2018), and recruited schools as part of a Consortium of schools leaders interested in implementing racial equity-focused SEL strategies (Authors, 2019). School leadership agreed to participate in a research-practice partnership related to the promotion of racial equity at each school. A variety of data sources were included in the case study which differed by school. Research took place in School 1 in Spring 2018, and in School 2 in Spring 2020.

School 1 is a middle school that serves over 850 students, 37% of whom met criteria for

free and reduced-price lunch (FRL). Of the 850 students, 35% were white, 28% Asian, 23%, Hispanic or Latino, 8% Multiracial, 6% Black and 1% Native Hawaiian, Pacific Islander or Native American/Alaskan Native. Approximately 85% of school staff identified as white. In Spring 2018, we met with school leadership (principal, two vice principals, and the Dean of students) to discuss their concerns and goals for the school. These administrators identified as a white male, two white women and a Black male. School leaders were concerned about the results of their school climate survey which shed light on bullying problems and racially disproportionate discipline outcomes. Data consisted of observational notes, focus groups and interviews, school climate and discipline data, and documents such as meeting minutes. We conducted two focus groups with school leadership (n=4), two focus groups with teachers (n=4), two focus groups with students (n=12), with one of those groups being only students of color.

School 2 is a middle school that serves over 700 students, 65% of whom qualify for FRL and who identify as 34% Black, 25% Asian, 19% Hispanic, 10% Multiracial, and 9% white. Approximately half of the school staff identified as white, but 75% of teaching staff were white. We first met with the racial equity team (RET) to discuss their goals. The RET was concerned about racially disproportionate discipline outcomes and a “culture of compliance” related to discipline which caused significant issues with school climate. Data consisted of observational notes, focus groups and interviews, a survey of school staff, school staff open-ended reflections, and documents. We conducted a survey of all school staff that included open-ended responses, interviewed 14 teachers, and conducted four interviews and one focus group with students (n=6).

Analysis

Pattern matching and cross-case synthesis were the analytical approaches used to conduct this multi-site case study (Yin, 2018). The unit of analysis for this study is the UACS project, with each project being one case. First, all data from both case studies were reviewed by the first

author. Initial themes were discussed with the research team. Themes were organized across the stages of the project, and successes and challenges within each stage were identified. Data and supporting quotes were then re-reviewed with the research team. We triangulated data across and within cases. This included having a diversity of data sources and types (e.g. survey, open-ended discussion, interview, artifacts from guided activities, and observation). Within each case, the collaborative analysis process enriched the trustworthiness of data interpretation.

Researcher Positionality

The first and second authors identify as cisgender white women from working-class backgrounds. The first author is a social work faculty member and studies racial equity in schools. The second author is a doctoral student who studies critical youth development. The third author identifies as a cisgender Black man who is a member of the social work who studies strategies to facilitate positive experiences and outcomes of BIPOC in racialized institutions. The fourth author, a Black woman and a social work professor. The fifth author is a cisgender Native Hawaiian male who is a senior faculty at a large, predominantly white research university.

Results

Building the Partnership

Successes. Partnership development occurred over the span of a year for each school in the study. Trust-building happened slowly and took many forms. At the beginning of the project, we met with school administrators twice at School 1 to discuss their goals, largely motivated by the results of their climate survey. School 1 wanted to focus on issues they were having with bullying, improve school climate overall, and promote racial equity. The climate survey showed negative scores on all bullying-related items, which reflected administrators' experiences of having significant challenges with responding to and preventing bullying, as well as promoting a positive, racially equitable school climate. At School 2, we met with the Racial Equity Team

(RET), who were interested in creating a project to improve the discipline process. The RET felt the discipline process enforced a “culture of compliance” which reinforced racial inequities. At both schools, it was crucial to focus on trust-building by spending time to learn about how each school thought and talked about issues of practice and develop relationships with formal and informal leaders of racial equity work in the school. This included accounting for power dynamics amongst and between educators and researchers. Across both cases, the university researchers facilitated school-based partners through critical dialogue before planning the project. Critical dialogue refers to “identifying, challenging, and reframing status quo discourses that can then be acted upon in new ways that challenge oppression and open opportunities for transformation” (p. 197, Laman et al., 2012). In doing so, the university members were able to learn more about how the school related to the issues of racial equity practice. We guided design teams through a process of thoughtfully defining a research question which when answered, will contribute to knowledge about promoting racial justice and equity to guide our work together.

It was an asset to the project and to building trust that the research team was multiracial. This helped to facilitate connections and trust with staff and students of color, allowing us to create spaces for BIPOC to feel safer sharing their experiences of racism and inequity within the school. Similarly, the presence of white researchers played a pivotal role in reducing defensiveness among white staff and students which helped to facilitate critical racial reflection and consciousness-building. For example, when the project started at School 1, the principal was highly motivated by having recently read *White Fragility* (DiAngelo, 2016). Through critical dialogue and semi-guided reflection with university researchers, he was better able to move beyond reductive critiques of whiteness and more critically question his responsibility in the school’s perpetuation and interruption of racism. He also encouraged teachers to prioritize efforts to reduce racism and bullying even if it meant taking time away from instruction.

Challenges. One of the main challenges to building a successful university-school partnership was navigating school hierarchies and power structures. In the case of School 1, the leaders of the racial equity work were the school administration. This was a mostly white group brought together by their roles and not necessarily a commitment of racial justice in the school. This structure reinforced existing power dynamics and marginalization of BIPOC student/educator voice by not including the people most and school staff who were in the position to improve racial equity practices. As a result, it was a challenge for the university team to build relationships with other educators in the school, as the administrative team served as gatekeepers to how much and what kinds of contact the researcher team had with teachers and students. Power dynamics at play were amplified by the fact that the leaders of the racial equity work were in positions of power with respect to work and identity. This contrasted with School 2, which operated with a RET from multiple roles, racial identities, and positionalities.

Designing the Project

Successes. Each project adopted participatory approaches working with school staff at each school. Co-creating the research plan facilitated buy-in from the planning team, and made sure the project was going to answer questions relevant to each school. We made an explicit effort to include the voices of BIPOC students impacted by racial inequities, and to shift the focus from students as the problem to the adults at the school needing to change. In designing data collection strategies at School 1, we created one group of just BIPOC students, led by a Black facilitator. Focus group protocol questions were written by the research team and reviewed and edited by administrators. Data from these focus groups were used in a data-to-action workshop co-designed by the research team and administrators. School staff were asked to read aloud student quotes to empathize with student experiences. The following quote is an example:

Interviewer 1: How do you know when someone is being treated unfairly at this school?

Student 6: Well, I feel like, if they call you names depending on your race. Like, where some, some guy called me a burrito. Or I think, sometimes they call me a beaner. Yeah.

Interviewer 1: How does that make you feel?

Student 6: I really don't care.

Student 7: They call me monkey. They call me a monkey. They, say like, "Shut up, with your big ears, big head, looking like a whole monkey." And they, I'll be giving back, that's like racist, to like towards black people.

Interviewer 1: Does it come from black people and other races? Or...

Student 7: Yeah, it comes from all races but like, yeah, it kind of bothers me.

Incorporating voices of color as the starting point contributed to de-centering whiteness by focusing on the lived experiences of BIPOC students at the school. This also served to increase teacher awareness about the problems faced by BIPOC students. In a post-workshop reflection, one teacher reported “I learned that we have some work ahead of us to collectively build a more positive and accepting learning environment.” and another said, “I learned about how our students feel in school with regards to peer interactions.”

Since the RET at School 2 was interested in improving disciplinary processes, they were more focused on school staff and their response to students. Reports of “defiance” and “disrespect” made up two-thirds of discipline referrals. To define the problem, we gave a survey on attitudes about and commitment to social justice and co-designed an activity with all school staff to create process maps of how a typical discipline process plays out. The pandemic began immediately after this workshop in March 2020. The school initially expressed commitment to continuing with the project, and we planned many more activities including a reflection survey that asked school staff to react to data on their colleagues' social justice attitudes, a professional development session, and a data-to-action workshop. The survey was developed by the research team based on RET team discussion and was approved by the RET team. Given the changing circumstances, we launched a series of smaller, but coordinated projects as part of the larger design.

Challenges. Inviting authentic participation of teachers and students was a challenge for different reasons at each school. At School 1, students' voices were included through their participation in focus groups, but students were not included as part of the analysis or strategic planning stages of the project. Teachers were also not included in the initial planning, and only four teachers participated in providing qualitative data. Teachers who attended focus groups or the interview had to volunteer their time outside of the school day. At School 2, the structure of the RET allowed for more authentic teacher engagement with the project, however, student voices were not integrated until the end of the project.

At both schools, the design process was limited by the imaginations and racial consciousness of the co-researchers (school staff) and research team. Positionality was a major factor in this limitation, as white participants, in the absence of deep reflexivity and antiracist commitment, have an implicit stake in maintaining the status quo. At School 1, conversations with white administrators revealed their investment in disciplinary processes remaining structured as is, despite these practices being linked to racial disparities. At School 2, discussions with staff became difficult as unchecked white fragility entered the conversation.

Additionally, it was difficult to integrate the partnership deeply into the schools' routine practices, which would have supported the sustainability of the racial equity-focused work. This resulted in the work being added to educators' many existing responsibilities. There was no set time during work hours for teachers to engage in a planning process, nor was there a way to elicit the feedback of people outside of the planning teams. Increasing the participation of other teachers, school staff, students, and parents of color would make the process more democratic and also further center voices that are marginalized from school research, planning, and action.

Analyzing the Data

Successes. After collecting data in various forms at both schools, data analysis was conducted in as participatory a manner as was possible at each school. At both schools, an initial coding of the data was completed by the research team, categorizing quotes as related to the major themes of interest for each school. We summarized each section and collected representative quotes to share with the planning teams. At workshops at each school, we reviewed the cycles of socialization and liberation to provide a shared language and framework for analyzing the data. The cycle of socialization lays out the ways that we are born into ignorance based on what our families and social institutions teach us about how the world works, especially with regard to privilege and oppression (Harro, 2000). The cycle of socialization was helpful framing to avoid the defensiveness that often arises when white folks first begin to learn about their complicity in racism. At School 1, in post-workshop reflections, many staff reflected on how helpful it was to learn about the cycle of socialization, saying “It was very enlightening. Really powerful - thank you!” and “ I learned about the cycle of socialization and what it looks like to get off of it. Change. Raise consciousness. Interrupt!”

At both schools, we engaged the entire school staff in a process of collaborative analysis of the data. During the data-to-action workshop at School 1, school staff were asked to read student quotes related to each of the three themes (race relations, bullying, school climate). We selected quotes to uplift the voices of BIPOC. This supported teachers to have a deeper understanding and connection to the issues faced by their students. After reading the quotes and having individual reflection time, school staff joined small groups to discuss how the themes that arose were connected to the cycle of socialization. From these themes, staff developed a problem statement relating to the themes then conducted a root cause analysis of the problem.

At School 2, we conducted two workshops. In the first workshop, we asked school staff to create process maps of the process of how disciplinary problems are handled. Process maps

layout visually the steps of the process of discipline with a series of boxes and arrows. A survey of attitudes and commitment to social justice was also administered. Following this survey, we administered an open-ended survey asking school staff to reflect on the data from two key questions from the survey that seemed to represent a point of tension at the school and a possible barrier to progress: 75% of school staff agreed that “Prejudice and discrimination limit the success of people of color,” while 59% of school staff disagreed with the statement, “All whites receive unearned privileges in US society.” At the second workshop, we reviewed the cycle of socialization and discussed quantitative data from the survey. We led critical dialogues to unpack the attitudes shown in the data and discuss how the school can build a better foundation for anti-racist work. A third workshop was scheduled to review qualitative interview data but was canceled to take the time allocated to prepare for school to be fully remote due to the pandemic.

The process of co-analysis created the space for critical dialogue and reflection on students’ and colleagues’ inner worlds in a way that would not have otherwise been possible. Using the data from the school staff and students as content for reflection deepened discussions about the state of racial equity efforts at the school, as problems could not be avoided or explained away. It made the problems come to life and informed conversations about consciousness development among staff. School staff were asked to critically reflect on how the school can better support students and move the school forward on the cycle of liberation rather than continuing to socialize and therefore accept the racial status quo. Engaging in critical co-analysis on the process map and root cause trees also illuminated leverage points for change.

Challenges. There was no student involvement in analysis, thus, student voices were limited, making their participation at a level of “assigned but informed” (Hart, 1992). Their voice was a crucial missing perspective and counter to our participatory goals. We also found that some teachers made problematic interpretations of the data based on their limited racial

consciousness and color-evasive racism. This was evident in one groups' root cause tree that was focused on a lack of kindness to each other, rather than seeing the presence of racism in the student quotes who were facing issues such as being called the N-word or other racist stereotypes. One staff said, "The conversation should have been around kindness as opposed to bullying," which misses the point. These challenges pointed to a need for ongoing critical dialogue to be able to engage with these topics, yet there was no structure to do so. Additionally, because there are existing power dynamics between school staff based on their roles in the school and typical identity-based systems of power and oppression, conversations on these important topics were restrained. In this way, structural racism and white privilege were reified.

Translating the Data into Action

Successes. The result of School 1's data-to-action workshop was a series of goals for school improvement planning. Learning communities each developed three actions they planned to take to improve racial equity based on learnings from the workshop. Personal growth and learnings to increase racial consciousness were evident in feedback and questions from the workshop. Teachers reflected that they want "more tools to combat racism" and one teacher learned that "not actively trying to change/teach about racism/white privilege is allowing it." At School 2, we did not do any school-level action planning because the final workshop was canceled. At an interim workshop, we led critical dialogues on how white fragility impacted the school's ability to make racial justice progress and how the ongoing events around George Floyd's murder had impacted staff engagement about issues of racism. While we did not engage in whole-school action planning, these actions did support staff to raise their awareness of racism in the school and develop skills in critical dialogue. One white teacher noted:

I think I've become more aware of my privilege. Like I am a privileged person and need to be aware that when I walk into a space where I'm in a position of power over children of so many different races and backgrounds who oftentimes don't trust adults.... And I

think my time at [School 2] has taught me to be aware of that in everything that I do.

Challenges. There were many instances at both schools where participants resisted change or systemic issues served as barriers. School 1 was the home of an “Emotional and Behavioral Disorder” (EBD) program, a special education program where students with these types of challenges were in a special classroom for most of the day. The paternalistic nature of the program reinforced racialized deficit narratives about student behavior. The acceptance and ubiquity of these deficit narratives made challenging these narratives in other spaces challenging and minimized the importance of incorporating student voice.

Further, it was difficult to gauge how transformational the process was for educators in the short or long term. Transforming white teacher racial consciousness is important, but not sufficient to address the racial disparities in education. The process was limited by wide gaps in racial consciousness between teachers. Given the constraints of the partnership, there were moments where the learning of less racially conscious white educators was unintentionally centered in the process, particularly for School 1. At School 2, we were able to create smaller projects within the larger design that more adequately allowed for BIPOC and more critically conscious white educators to shape the process.

Discussion

Research-practice partnerships for the purposes of promoting racial justice in schools are a significant venture that has the potential to reshape school environments and improve academic and social outcomes for all students. While this is certainly not the first project to undertake this aim, this paper contributes to the body of knowledge on the processes of development, design, analysis, and translating data to action across two sites through an articulation of the successes and challenges we faced. Even when members of the research partnership are committed to the core principles of participatory practice, our own blinders and positions can present issues of

western or white-centered, paternalistic, and top-down mechanisms in project design and implementation. Factors out of the team's control, such as changing circumstances for school partners, the impact of the murder of George Floyd, or the pandemic, presented opportunities and challenges. Despite these challenges, we observed many successful processes and outcomes.

One of the main themes of this multisite case study is the importance of understanding the role of expertise and power in our relationship with schools. Schools often enter into partnerships with researchers to solve a problem. While schools may understand that their expertise is also needed and are willing to contribute, they may want researchers to do the heavy lifting and report back. Others within schools may have an investment in the partnership, while having questions of who holds knowledge and power in a research partnership. Identifying processes for shared power, shared governance, and co-creation of knowledge shifts the weight of expertise and power from researchers to schools, promoting equity in voices and modeling the goals of racial justice that are desired. While many of these principles and processes were built into our development and design, power dynamics were present throughout our project.

Perhaps the clearest example of this was the attention given to youth voices within the context of racial equity in schools. While we were successful in incorporating youth voices explicitly in School 1, we did not include them until the end of the project for School 2. Youth voices were not present at planning meetings or in analyzing the data. Having a diverse research staff had many advantages for soliciting the experiences of both respondents who were white and BIPOC. It facilitated relationships as members of the team could relate to the problem through their own experiences of inequity in schools. The extent to which our school partners were diverse in their racial composition, but also in their varying levels of racial consciousness also facilitated both successes and challenges. This will almost always be true when working in the area of racial justice that some partners will be invested in change while others are invested in

maintaining the status quo. Anticipating these differences and designing activities that promote critical reflection is necessary, even if they uncover that the problem is deeply rooted.

Finally, in translating data into action, it is critical that planning for sustainable action occurs at the beginning of the partnership and to identify the change levers necessary for praxis early in the process. We chose to utilize data-to-action workshops as a means for promoting sustainable action. While we were only able to complete this process at School 1 due to the pandemic, the partnership helped to establish concrete steps toward racial justice to be sustained beyond the partnership. Although the final workshop did not occur in School 2, members of the partnership and survey and interview respondents expressed their desire to continue learning about racial justice and hoped to revisit these issues once schools are out of the crisis.

Overall, this case study highlights the powerful and crucial role of student and teacher voices in developing and implementing racial equity-focused strategies. Social workers are well positioned in schools to lead racial equity work. Initiatives aimed at racial equity within institutions are often top-down in nature. If it comes from the bottom up, it is often in the form of activism that calls for greater attention to racial justice. Research-practice partnerships have the opportunity to serve as an intermediary to this process, whether schools are responding to policy, crisis, or a deep commitment. Partnerships based on principles of equity, racial and social justice, and the inclusion of all voices, have a greater chance of making successful change. Opportunities for collaboration between researchers and schools for racial justice could be more readily available as the evolution of anti-racism post George Floyd's murder and post-pandemic, which highlighted racial inequities in schools and in society. Partnerships offer an opportunity for both embedding ourselves in schools and in understanding the levers necessary for new practices or policies that promote racial justice to emerge. School social workers, with their training in racial and social justice, can be leaders in this work, and serve as connectors between researchers and

school systems.

A major limitation of this study is the incompleteness of our data-to-action workshop at School 2 as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although we did not complete the final workshop, we did not abandon our relationship and rather shifted our focus to assisting them with understanding how the pandemic's impact. While we continued to try and steer the partnership back to racial justice, it was clear that the realities of COVID-19 were fully incapacitating the school and the momentum of the project. We still hope to revisit this school when there is willingness. The amount of data generated from this project was both a positive and a limitation. This paper represents our first attempt to summarize our processes across two sites. More refined analyses of the components outlined in this paper are warranted for future research. Specifically, more research on translation to action outcomes over a sustained period of time would be useful to understanding how research-practice partnerships action steps lead to a reduction in racial inequities within schools. Further, we encourage the use of research-practice partnerships as a role in which researchers can impact racial justice within schools.

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Table 1. Successes and challenges of a research-practice partnership in promoting racial equity

Stage	Successes	Challenges
Building the Partnership	Trust building <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meeting with school leaders ● Built on problem of practice identified by the school 	Hierarchical structures/power dynamics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited engagement of important stakeholders, no parental involvement ● Lack of structural support for partnership activities
	Positionality and reflexivity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Commitment to racial equity among school leaders and willingness to do the work ● Diversity among university partners 	Competing activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Teacher time not supported ● No dedicated planning time ● Immediate needs take precedence
Designing the Project	Co-creation of research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitated commitment to the project ● Built in mechanism to ensure findings would be translatable and relevant 	Authentic participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limits on the inclusion of youth voice to providing data, not analyzing data or being a part of follow up
	Voices of color and youth voice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Youth voice/engagement ● Centering qualitative experiences of BIPOC youth 	Positionality and reflexivity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design limited by participant’s racial consciousness
Analyzing the Data	Building a shared language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cycles of socialization and liberation as shared framework for analysis 	Analysis limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students were not involved in data analysis - important missing perspective ● First round of analysis was only shared with ret at school 2, not whole school ● Problematic interpretations based on color evasive ideologies ● Ongoing critical dialogue needed, but not supported by the structures/time allocated
	Critical dialogue <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research process provides insights into inner worlds of youth and colleagues that would not have otherwise been possible ● Reflecting on consciousness development Collaborative analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● School-wide participation in data analysis ● Team code to categorize then have small groups take the quotes to analyze the qualitative quotes 	Restrained critical dialogue <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Power dynamics among school staff ● School staff’s professional workspace which limits level of authenticity/risk)
Translating the Data into Action	School improvement planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● School-wide goal setting 	Resistance to change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● History of racism and special education - deficit narratives, racialization ● No data on follow through and not enough emphasis on implementation
	Individual consciousness raising <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Staff developing critical dialogue skills, increasing skill in discussing difficult issues, and being reflexive. ● Role of the cycle of socialization in addressing potential for defensiveness 	Pandemic disruptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Covid-19 interrupting the data to action workshop, antiracism on the backburner